

FEATURES OF ECONOMIC SECURITY SYSTEMS

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ANNOTATION

The article analyzes the negative factors and threats to the economic security of small businesses. Relevant conclusions and proposals for planning a set of measures to optimize some aspects of prevention, planning and management of possible damage are given

Keywords: *small business, economic security, threats, negative factors, damage, internal threat, external threat*

INTRODUCTION. Globalization of the economy, which is a natural evolutionary process of society's development, exacerbates the problems of competitiveness and economic security at the national level. National security depends on the effectiveness of the economic security system and is achieved by ensuring the security of all subsystems that make up the socio-economic system of the state. Economic security is one of the most important. The basis of ensuring the economic security of the national economy is the ability of its legal entities to withstand modern challenges and threats arising under the influence of external and internal factors.

Thus, ensuring economic security can be characterized as a strategic direction in the activities of individual enterprises and the state as a whole. For all enterprises, especially for enterprises that do not have their own security service, the issues of ensuring economic security are the most urgent. Enterprises that do not have such specialized departments should have departments or employees that provide certain

types of economic security, for example, information, personnel, production, environmental, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY. The most common way to determine the economic security of an enterprise is the resource approach. To ensure economic security, the enterprise uses a combination of the following resources:

1) capital resource. The authorized capital of the company, together with the borrowed financial resources, forms the basis of the enterprise and allows obtaining and maintaining other corporate resources that were not initially available to the founders of the enterprise;

2) personnel resource. Managers, engineers and technicians of the enterprise, production workers and workers, with their knowledge, experience and skills, are the main links that manage and connect all factors of this business, ensure the implementation of the entrepreneurial ideology and the achievement of business goals;

3) information and technology resource. Scientific, technical and technological information about all aspects of business, changes in the political, social, economic and environmental situation, information about the company's markets, as well as new business organization and management methods. Adequate and timely response to changes in the external environment, business environment, effective planning and implementation of one's business activities;

4) machine and equipment resource. Based on the available financial, information technology and personnel resources, the company buys the necessary and cheap equipment.

5) property rights resource. This resource includes the right to use intellectual property objects, license and quota for the use of natural resources, land use rights. The use of this resource allows the company to participate in advanced technological developments without carrying out its own expensive research and development.

RESULTS. Sinyavskaya T.G. and Tregubova A.A. and states that the concepts of risk and threat should be distinguished more clearly. According to their scientific hypothesis, risk is the potential loss of resources or income associated with a particular alternative. Risk and management are inextricably linked. Economic risk occurs as a

result of the impact of certain risks and threats, i.e., in cases where the situation that occurred under certain objective conditions has a probabilistic nature. Danger, in turn, is interpreted there as "an opportunity, a threat of something very bad, some kind of misfortune." That is, in a certain sense, threat and risk can be considered synonymous. Unlike risk, threat is broadly understood and refers to a situation characterized by the possibility of negative and positive outcomes. Therefore, threats and hazards represent some sources of risk.

DISCUSSIONS. V. Abramov describes that, despite the similarity of actions of destabilizing factors in a single economic space, the forms of manifestation of threats to economic security at different levels of the hierarchy of organizational and economic structures are different. These global factors include the general decline in production, the collapse of the financial system, the increase in social tensions, the criminalization of society and the economy, the further weakening of competitiveness, and others. There are many classifications of threats to the economic security of the enterprise in various literature: 1) by source (internal, external); 2) according to the nature of the incident (political, criminal, competitive, counterparty, etc.); 3) according to the probability of implementation (real, potential); 4) object of attack (data, employees, finances, goods, material assets, business reputation, etc.); 5) predict if possible (predictable, unpredictable); 6) according to the size of the expected damage (catastrophic, significant, causing difficulty); 7) other classification features.

CONCLUSION. Most small businesses specialize in one area. The nature of production does not allow a quick transition to the production of other products, if necessary. It also poses certain threats: 1) increased competition in the market of products produced by a highly specialized enterprise; 2) increased competition in the region is important in cases where the transportation of these products leads to a significant increase in prices for the consumer (primary industry, production of a number of goods); 3) decrease in demand for manufactured products due to objective reasons; 4) unfair competition in all its forms; 5) market monopolization.

In addition to the existence of personal threats, there are also many factors that cause threats to the economic security of the company. Knowing these factors will help

to identify and eliminate them, and therefore reduce the likelihood of threats to the economic security of the company.

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